

Efficient Multi-Column LU Factorization Updates for Exact Linear Programming

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Abstract. State-of-the-art exact linear programming (LP) solvers combine numerical computations and exact arithmetic to guarantee their outputs’ correctness. They rely on floating-point arithmetic to perform the steps of the simplex algorithm, culminating in a basic solution and terminating status (optimality, infeasibility, etc.). To validate whether the terminating status is correct or to indicate if further adjustments and simplex iterations are needed, these solvers then use exact arithmetic to obtain the primal and dual solutions—typically via LU factorization algorithms—of the final basis. To improve the performance of these solvers on highly ill-conditioned problems that require multiple exact basis validations, this work develops LU factorization update algorithms that combine floating-point and exact arithmetic to efficiently reflect the replacement of multiple columns in the basis. The process entails performing a valid sequence of single-column replacement updates. We prove that such sequences can be determined at runtime and devise algorithms that integrate floating-point and exact arithmetic for executing the LU updates efficiently. We incorporate the methodology into the exact solver QSOpt_ex and apply it on well-known benchmark datasets and additional numerically challenging problems generated herein using perturbations.

Funding: This research was supported by NSF Award # 2340527 and NSF REU Award # 2349179.

Key words: Exact linear programming, LU factorization, rational arithmetic.

1. Introduction

Since its inception nearly 80 years ago, linear programming (LP) has made significant leaps in practice. Despite these advances, software that implement LP methods remain susceptible to roundoff errors that arise from the use of floating-point arithmetic. The accumulation of roundoff errors in solver subroutines can lead to incongruous outputs, such as reporting a suboptimal solution as optimal, reporting an infeasible solution as optimal, or misidentifying a problem as infeasible (Klotz and Newman 2013a). This numerical instability is compounded in mixed-integer linear programming (MIP), where branch-and-bound algorithms rely on the correct solution of numerous LP relaxations. An error in solving one of these subproblems can compromise the entire branch-and-bound tree (Hoen and Gleixner 2025, Klotz and Newman 2013b).

To address these numerical challenges, specialized solvers have been developed to guarantee the solution’s correctness efficiently, by combining mixed precision floating-point arithmetic and exact computations. Two prominent examples are QSOpt_ex (Applegate et al. 2007) and SoPlex (Gleixner and Steffy 2020, Gleixner et al. 2016, Eifler et al. 2025). QSOpt_ex employs a “certify-and-repair” strategy; Figure 1a illustrates the steps of its baseline configuration. At first, it attempts to solve the problem via the standard floating-point primal-dual simplex algorithm, culminating in a basic solution and terminating status (optimality, infeasibility, etc.). The initial floating-point solve is completed in native precision, α_0 (usually in *double* precision, i.e., 64 bits). Afterwards, QSOpt_ex performs an *exact basis validation* (EBV), which entails solving for the primal and dual

(a) Baseline Configuration: Precision-Boosting Simplex with LU Basis Validation

(b) Update Configuration: Baseline Configuration Enhanced with Multi-Column LU Updates

Figure 1 Execution Configuration of Baseline (i.e., Current) and Update (i.e., Proposed) Exact LP Solvers

solutions corresponding to the final basis in exact rational arithmetic to verify whether the purported terminating status is correct. If the latter process fails—e.g., the floating-point simplex claims to have found an optimal solution, but the exact primal and/or dual solution contain negative values—QSOpt_ex boosts the current floating-point precision α by δ (i.e., $\alpha \leftarrow \alpha + \delta$) and repeats the process, “warm-starting” from the previous solution, if possible.

SoPlex also combines mixed precision and exact arithmetic operations, although its strategy is more nuanced. It deploys an advanced technique known as *LP iterative refinement*, which repeatedly solves a series of modified LPs in floating-point arithmetic, with each subsequent problem correcting for residual errors. The solver has recently included precision boosting to further enhance its capabilities on numerically challenging problems (Eifler et al. 2025). Nonetheless, it too relies on EBV as a final backstop against potential errors stemming from its floating point-based subroutines. The focus of the present work is on improving the performance of EBV subroutines, with our implementation centered on QSOpt_ex due to its more manageable code base and the relative ease of modifying its core routines. Nonetheless, given the fundamental role of EBV, the findings are relevant to other exact LP and exact MIP implementations.

2. Background

Modern simplex-based solvers and LU factorizations go hand-in-hand. In the traditional simplex algorithm, these factorizations are the main subroutine for efficiently solving systems of linear equations (SLEs) necessary to obtain a basic solution and to move between one such solution to the next. The simplex algorithm *pivots* or iteratively moves between adjacent extreme points of the feasible region, each with a basis matrix, A_B , while improvement from the current point is possible. Each pivot requires solving multiple SLEs including $A_B x = b$ for the current basic solution, x ; $A_B^T \pi = c_B$ for the the dual solution, π ; and $A_B d = a_j$ for the direction vector, d . The SLEs are usually solved using LU factorization algorithms, which decompose the basis matrix A_B into a lower-triangular matrix L and an upper-triangular matrix U such that $A_B = LU$. Once L and U are known, solving the SLE $A_B x = b$ is reduced to two simple triangular solves: first $Ly = b$

(a) Initial U Factor (b) Spike Insertion (c) Permutations (d) Row Eliminations
Figure 2 Steps Performed on Upper-triangular Factor U by the Saunders LU Update Algorithm

for y (forward solve) and then $Ux = y$ for x (backward solve). LU factorization algorithms are especially useful in the simplex method, because they are more numerically stable than calculating the matrix inverse. They are also better at exploiting and preserving sparsity, which is common to most real-world LPs.

LU update algorithms can yield additional computational benefits, by taking advantage of a key feature of the simplex method: each pivot involves changing just one column in the basis matrix. These update algorithms efficiently modify the existing L and U factors to reflect a single-column replacement. A common LU update strategy, used in `QSopt_ex`, is the eponymous update by Saunders (1973); it is illustrated in Figure 2. The procedure involves replacing the leaving column in U with a “spike vector” derived from the entering column (Figure 2b), permuting rows and columns to relocate this spike (Figure 2c), and then performing a series of row eliminations to restore the upper-triangular structure (Figure 2d). These elimination operations are stored as elementary matrices that modify the L matrix. While updates are fast, they have trade-offs. Repeated updates can lead to “fill-in”, that is, changing zeros in the matrix factors to non-zeros, which slows down computations and increases memory usage. To manage this, solvers typically re-factorize after a set number of updates (Chvátal 1983).

`QSopt_ex` incorporates exact rational arithmetic versions of common LU factorization subroutines, but it does not currently utilize exact update algorithms. This omission is expected, given the high cost of performing simplex iterations in exact rational arithmetic. However, it overlooks another prospective use case for these algorithms on highly ill-conditioned problems that cause the floating-point solver to return an incorrect terminating status. Namely, it may be possible to take advantage of the potential similarity in the final bases evaluated in consecutive EBV steps to avoid having to construct a new exact LU factorization from scratch each time. Yet, unlike the standard use case of factorization updates involving a single column swap, consecutive final bases usually differ by several columns. As is discussed in the next section, handling a multi-column update is more complicated than the standard single-column replacement update. In short, improper update sequences can easily lead to invalid outcomes, such as encountering a singular matrix during the update process. The primary contributions of this work are to introduce and implement theory and algorithms for avoiding such failures.

3. Exact Multi-Column LU Updates

The section develops and proves the correctness of an efficient algorithm for performing a multi-column LU update, with which the replacement of multiple columns of a matrix can be efficiently reflected onto an existing LU factorization of that matrix. In the context of exact LP, the algorithm is called whenever the basic solution returned by a (floating-point) simplex solve fails an EBV step,

Figure 3 Swapping x_1 with x_7 in the Basis Represented by the Red Asterisk Yields a Singular Matrix

that is, when the solver's terminating status is contradicted by the exact primal and/or dual solutions of the final basis. This event triggers the need for additional simplex pivots in higher floating-point precision that culminate in a modified basis that must then undergo EBV again, motivating the development of exact LU update algorithms for carrying out the process efficiently.

The algorithm entails three main steps: (1) Store the exact LU factorization and column ordering of an initial basis matrix, A_B ; (2) assuming a new basis, \hat{A}_B , has been returned by the solver, compare its column indices to those from the stored basis to identify the *mismatches*, that is, the subsets of columns that are unique to each basis; (3) perform a sequence of single-column LU updates onto the stored factorization, $LU(A_B)$, to resolve the mismatches. The resulting factorization, $LU(\hat{A}_B)$, corresponds to what would be obtained if the exact LU factorization of the new basis had been instead constructed from scratch (except potentially for its column ordering). Figure 1b depicts how this update algorithm fits within the QSopt_ex framework.

These steps entailed various modifications to the QSopt_ex codebase. For example, it was necessary to add a deep copy function to extract and store the exact LU factorization and to incorporate functions that align the columns of the bases returned by the floating-point solves (since QSopt_ex discards their ordering). The most significant changes and complex challenge stem from the sequence of single-column replacement updates that need to be performed to transition from $LU(A_B)$ to $LU(\hat{A}_B)$. Choosing pairs of indices arbitrarily from the sets of mismatches can cause the process to fail. This occurs when, during a column swap, the column selected to enter is linearly dependent with the other $n - 1$ columns, causing the working matrix to become singular.

To illustrate this potential issue, consider Figure 3, which plots the feasible region of a two-variable LP defined by seven inequalities. Therein, the variables represent the constraint that becomes tight along the adjoining hyperplane—i.e., when the associated variable becomes non-basic (i.e., equal to 0) in the standard form of the problem. We focus on the non-basic variable sets, since they are complementary to the basic variable sets but smaller in size. Let the initial non-basic variable set be $N = \{x_1, x_2\}$, and the target non-basic set be $\hat{N} = \{x_6, x_7\}$ (the corresponding intersections are marked with a red and a blue asterisk on the plot). Hence, the number of mismatches is $|B \setminus \hat{B}| = |\hat{B} \setminus B| = |\hat{N} \setminus N| = |N \setminus \hat{N}| = 2$, which indicates that moving N into \hat{N} requires at least two column swaps (i.e., pivots). There are four initial choices for swapping a pair of mismatched elements: $x_1 \leftrightarrow x_6$, $x_1 \leftrightarrow x_7$, $x_2 \leftrightarrow x_6$, and $x_2 \leftrightarrow x_7$.

However, an arbitrary choice can fail. Swapping x_2 (entering) with x_6 (leaving), the intermediate basis has the non-basic set $N' = \{x_1, x_7\}$. However, as the figure illustrates, the hyperplanes for x_1 and x_7 are parallel, indicating that their intersection is undefined. Therefore, the corresponding intermediate matrix (i.e., A'_B) is singular, and the update is invalid. Consequently, the order of column swaps becomes critical, prompting the derivation of sequences that are guaranteed to work. It is equally important to keep the sequence as short as possible to minimize using exact arithmetic.

A seemingly straightforward approach for obtaining a valid sequence is to follow the floating-point simplex pivots that are performed between consecutive EBV steps. However, this proves to be highly impractical, as the number of such pivots often exceeds the number of mismatches—for certain of the instances herein considered, it was over 100x larger! Such a strategy is tantamount to switching to exact pivoting after the initial basis validation, which is ill-advised (Applegate et al. 2007). Moreover, the prospect of finding a significantly shorter sequence consisting of basic feasible solutions is unlikely to be fruitful. In preliminary tests, the shortest such path was often no shorter than the path followed by the floating-point simplex pivots.

The remainder of this section demonstrates that by expanding the search to include infeasible basic solutions, a short and valid sequence of column replacements can always be obtained. The formal underpinnings for this guarantee are derived from the theory of *matroids*, which represent a mathematical structure that generalizes the notion of linear independence from vector spaces.

DEFINITION 1 (MATROID). A matroid consists of a finite set of elements called the ground set and a collection of subsets called independent sets.

DEFINITION 2 (BASIS OF A MATROID). A matroid basis is a maximal independent set; that is, a set B is a basis if B is independent and no proper superset of B is independent.

Next, we restate a fundamental result that serves as the building block for the target sequence of column replacements.

Matroid basis exchange property. Given two bases B_1 and B_2 and any element $\beta \in B_1 \setminus B_2$, there exists an element $\gamma \in B_2 \setminus B_1$ such that $(B_1 \setminus \{\beta\}) \cup \{\gamma\}$ is also a basis.

This provides a theoretical guarantee that a mismatched element from B_1 can be swapped with one from B_2 while maintaining a valid basis. In the context of linear programming, the ground set is the set of all column vectors of the constraint matrix, the independent sets are the selections that are linearly independent, and simplex bases are matroid bases. Hence, the matroid exchange property establishes that there exists a path of single-column swaps linking two bases whose length is equal to the number of mismatches between them. Note, however, that this property does not specify how the sequence can be determined.

To find a valid swap at each step, we introduce an algorithm that adapts a core step from the simplex method, namely the minimum ratio test. Recall that, in the standard definition of this subroutine, the leaving variable is chosen by determining the smallest non-negative ratio within the direction vector to avoid singularity and infeasible basic solutions. The proposed algorithm is less restrictive, as maintaining non-singularity is the only relevant concern (i.e., the goal is simply to reach a predetermined basis, as opposed to achieving a better objective function value with each pivot). Satisfying this requirement is guaranteed by a standard result of linear algebra, restated in the following, for completeness.

PROPOSITION 1. Let A_B be a basis matrix, a_j be a non-basic column, and $d = A_B^{-1}a_j$ be the simplex direction vector. For an update swapping a_r with a_j , $d_r \neq 0$ if and only if the new basis matrix \hat{B} is non-singular.

As an implication of this looser exiting variable criterion, it is often necessary to move outside of the feasibility region. For the Figure 3 example, there is a shortcut path requiring only two steps (drawn using dotted lines) that circumvents the longer path connecting the two bases in the feasible space. The first pivot moves from the basis represented by non-basic variables $N = \{x_1, x_2\}$ to an intermediate infeasible basic solution represented by non-basic variables $N' = \{x_2, x_6\}$ (marked with a purple asterisk). The second pivot returns to the feasible space at the target basic solution represented by non-basic variables $\hat{N} = \{x_6, x_7\}$.

THEOREM 1. *Let B and \hat{B} be two index sets representing two simplex bases with induced coefficient matrices A_B and $A_{\hat{B}}$, respectively. Additionally, let $m = |B \setminus \hat{B}|$ be the number of mismatches, where $0 \leq m \leq |B|$. A sequence of m column swaps can be constructed to transition from A_B into $A_{\hat{B}}$, while maintaining linear independence of columns/rows, by iteratively choosing an entering index $j \in B$ and a leaving index $r \in \hat{B}$ such that j, r are in their respective current mismatch sets.*

Proof. To demonstrate how each element of the sequence is determined, define the individual bases via the index sets $B = B_{(0)}, B_{(1)}, B_{(2)}, \dots, B_{(m)}$. For any index set S , let A_S denote the matrix whose columns are given by $\{a_i, i \in S\}$. Additionally, define $\Delta_{in} := \hat{B} \setminus B$ and $\Delta_{out} := B \setminus \hat{B}$ as the entering set and leaving set, respectively, of basic variables. Then, the number of mismatches is given by $m = |\Delta_{out}| = |\Delta_{in}|$. The target basis matrix $A_{\hat{B}}$ is obtained through a sequence of m single-column swaps that begin at A_B .

Prior to determining the k th element in the sequence, the current basis is given by $B_{(k-1)}$. Now, select an arbitrary index j from the set of remaining entering variables, $\hat{B} \setminus B_{(k-1)}$; the corresponding column is a_j . Based on Proposition 1, index r can be selected as a leaving variable if and only if the corresponding coefficient d_r in the direction vector $d = (B_{(k-1)})^{-1}a_j$ is non-zero. The matroid exchange property guarantees that such a nonzero can be found from the set of remaining leaving indices, $B_{(k-1)} \setminus \hat{B}$. Thus, $B_{(k)} = (B_{(k-1)} \setminus \{r\}) \cup \{j\}$ is guaranteed to represent a basis, and we can swap j with r in $B_{(k-1)}$ —equivalently, replace column a_j of $A_{B_{(k-1)}}$ with a_r —to obtain $B_{(k)}$. This new basis has one more index in common with \hat{B} , and the number of mismatches is reduced by one.

After m iterations, all indices from the initial leaving set, Δ_{out} , have been removed from $B_{(0)}$ and all indices from the entering set, Δ_{in} , have been added to $B_{(0)}$ without encountering singular intermediate matrices. Therefore, the resulting basis $B_{(m)}$ is identical to the target basis matrix \hat{B} , and the matrix formed by these columns, $A_{B_{(m)}}$, coincides exactly with the target basis $A_{\hat{B}}$. \square

The previous proof provides a blueprint for finding a valid and short sequence of column replacement updates to perform on $LU(A_B)$; Algorithm 1 provides the corresponding pseudocode to fill in the details. Note that many possible shortcut sequences may be possible, depending on the plausible choices of entering and leaving indices, which are determined at runtime. Specifications of certain steps within Algorithm 1 are in order. First, the algorithm deploys a mixed-precision strategy that balances precision with performance. In effect, it utilizes floating-point precision to perform an auxiliary subroutine that guides the exact arithmetic multi-column update process. Specifically, the direction vector is computed using a moderate-level of precision α_1 —set to 128 bits in our implementation—and the direction coefficient with the highest magnitude is selected as the pivot index. This strategy is necessary, as computing the direction vector in exact arithmetic can pose a significant performance bottleneck (it often required more than half of the total LU update computation time in preliminary tests). Moreover, note that the mixed-precision exiting variable criterion is analogous to partial pivoting in Gaussian Elimination (Wilkinson 1961). In the usual application of this criterion, choosing a large pivot element helps minimize round-off error propagation. In the present context, it reduces the risk of selecting a zero-valued pivot that may be falsely interpreted as being non-zero due to numerical error. The remaining steps of each column replacement update are performed in exact arithmetic using the Saunders update (see Section 2), and the process continues until all the mismatches between the bases are resolved, resulting in the exact target factorization, $\hat{L}\hat{U} = A_{\hat{B}}$.

It is worth adding that, although a simultaneous rank- k update using the Sherman-Morrison-Woodbury (SMW) formula offers an alternative to performing multi-column replacements in the basis (Hager 1989), in practice it is preferred to apply a sequence of LU updates. The SMW approach requires access to the basis inverse, which is not natively stored in `QSopt_ex`. Calculating

Algorithm 1 Multi-Column LU Update

Require: Initial Basis B with factorization L, U , Target Basis \hat{B} .

Ensure: Final Basis \hat{B} with its correct, exact factorization $\hat{L}\hat{U}$.

```

1: Initialization:
2:  $B_{(0)} \leftarrow B, L_{(0)} \leftarrow L, U_{(0)} \leftarrow U$ 
3:  $\Delta_{in} \leftarrow \hat{B} \setminus B$  ▷ Set of entering columns
4:  $\Delta_{out} \leftarrow B \setminus \hat{B}$  ▷ Set of leaving columns
5:  $m \leftarrow |\Delta_{out}|$  ▷ Number of mismatches
6: for  $k = 1$  to  $m$  do
7:   Choose an entering column  $a_j \in \Delta_{in}$ .
8:   Compute direction vector  $d \leftarrow (B_{(k-1)})^{-1}a_j$  (in  $\alpha_1$  precision).
9:   Select leaving column index  $r \leftarrow \arg \max_{l \in \Delta_{out}} |d_l|$ . Let  $a_r$  be the column in  $B_{(k-1)}$  at index  $r$ .
10:   $(L_{(k)}, U_{(k)}) \leftarrow LU\text{-Update}(L_{(k+1)}, U_{(k+1)}, a_j, r)$  (in rational arithmetic).
11:   $B_{(k)} \leftarrow (B_{(k+1)} \setminus \{a_r\}) \cup \{a_j\}$ .
12:   $\Delta_{in} \leftarrow \Delta_{in} \setminus \{a_j\}, \Delta_{out} \leftarrow \Delta_{out} \setminus \{a_r\}$ .
13: end for
    
```

and storing the basis inverse can rival and even exceed the costs of LU re-factorization, especially under exact arithmetic (Escobedo et al. 2018). In fact, the inverse matrix tends to be very dense, even when the basis is sparse (Xia et al. 2015). Therefore, the “fill-in” and excessive memory consumption engendered by the SMW formula would likely offset any savings from avoiding exact basis re-factorization. Finally, reflecting basis column replacements in exact arithmetic via tailored rank-1 updates has been shown to be slower than traditional simplex updates (Escobedo 2024).

4. Results and Discussion

All tests were performed on a Dell Inc. Precision 7875 Tower running Linux Ubuntu 22.04.5. This workstation has a Dell 0T2RP3 motherboard, an AMD Ryzen Threadripper PRO 7995WX CPU, and 8x64GB Hynix RAM. QSopt_ex version 2.5.10 was compiled with the GNU Multi Precision Arithmetic Library (GMP) version 6.3 (Granlund and GD 2023). The GMP library provides the data structures and C functions for handling the high-precision floating-point and exact rational types and computations used by QSopt_ex.

To evaluate the impact of the proposed algorithms, we compare the performance of two solver configurations. The *baseline configuration* corresponds to the original QSopt_ex implementation, which performs a full, exact LU factorization for each exact validation. The *update configuration* corresponds to a QSopt_ex modification that uses the proposed multi-column LU update, starting from the second exact basis validation (when applicable).

The initial test set comprised a selection of problem instances from NETLIB (Gay 1985), MIPLIB 2010 (Koch et al. 2011), MIPLIB 2017 (Gleixner et al. 2021), and the LP test sets curated by Casaba Mészáros (Mészáros n.d.). All mixed-integer problems were relaxed to their corresponding linear programs. This collection substantially overlaps with the benchmark set presented in Espinoza (2006), which performs a comprehensive evaluation of QSopt_ex. We note, however, that many instances previously reported therein to require extended-precision arithmetic were successfully solved using standard double-precision arithmetic. This discrepancy likely stems from improvements in computer architecture and in the implementation of double-precision floating-point arithmetic since the date of publication of that work.

To identify the most computationally challenging instances from the compilation of 356 problems, we applied a multi-stage filtering process. First, we excluded problems that do not require extended precision, that is, those that pass the initial basis validation; this yielded 78 problems. From this reduced set, we excluded those whose total number of mismatches is greater than 500; this shrunk

Table 1 The Update Configuration Outperforms the Baseline Configuration on Nearly All Hard Instances

Problem	Baseline Config. Total Time (s)	Update Config. Total Time (s)	Baseline 2nd EBV Time (s)	Update 2nd EBV Time (s)	Mismatch Ratio	Speedup of 2nd EBV
50v-10_LP	0.038	0.049	0.006	0.011	1/233 (0.43%)	0.51
cycle	0.126	0.143	0.009	0.017	1/1903 (0.05%)	0.54
nesm	0.155	0.173	0.013	0.029	8/662 (1.21%)	0.46
cbs-cta_LP	2.804	N/A	0.025	1.354	264/10112 (2.61%)	0.02
ger50.17.t	0.507	0.506	0.035	0.040	1/499 (0.20%)	0.89
delf033	0.675	0.864	0.088	0.269	68/3173 (2.14%)	0.33
large001	0.872	1.001	0.113	0.239	39/4162 (0.94%)	0.47
neos-4722	7.793	8.591	0.142	0.930	3/113555 (0.003%)	0.15
uccase9_LP	77.612	77.553	0.169	0.996	21/49565 (0.04%)	0.17
ge	3.097	3.060	0.211	0.172	1/10099 (0.01%)	1.22
pilot.we*	0.899	0.859	0.262	0.217	0/722 (0.00%)	1.20
dff001	32.390	31.433	0.330	0.267	7/6071 (0.12%)	1.23
large009	1.836	2.517	0.412	1.081	99/4237 (2.34%)	0.38
ran14x18-dis	2.746	2.157	1.234	0.628	4/447 (0.89%)	1.97
dano3.3_LP	18.770	17.705	1.609	0.437	4/3202 (0.12%)	3.68
dano3.5_LP	18.823	17.718	1.611	0.439	4/3202 (0.12%)	3.67
pilot.ja*	6.493	4.245	2.764	0.522	0/940 (0.00%)	5.29
model6	7.148	5.253	2.791	0.934	2/2096 (0.10%)	2.99
d2q06c	19.162	12.266	8.351	1.348	1/2171 (0.05%)	6.20
pilot	87.697	57.359	43.479	13.339	10/1441 (0.69%)	3.26
pilot87	1373.367	1039.282	659.551	328.429	53/2030 (2.61%)	2.01
stat96v5*	2106.810	4483.910	849.520	3293	85/2307 (3.68%)	0.26

the dataset to 29 problems. Note that, while QSOpt_ex typically enforces a limit of 100 updates for floating-point factorizations, we opted for a more conservative bound based on the fundamental differences with the featured context. For similar reasons, we further filtered out instances with a mismatch ratio ($\frac{\#mismatches}{\#columns}$) greater than 5%, narrowing the problem set to 22 instances.

4.1. Performance on Compilation of Numerically Challenging Benchmark Instances

Table 1 displays the results, focusing on the EBV metrics to emphasize the performance impact of the update subroutines. The table reports, for each configuration, total time and second EBV time (no instance required more than two validation steps). The second EBV time serves as the primary metric for evaluating the proposed updates, as total execution time includes floating-point simplex durations that vary significantly across instances and do not reflect the efficiency of the exact LU update subroutines. It also reports the mismatch ratio ($\frac{\#mismatches}{\#columns}$), and the speedup of the second EBV, defined as ($\frac{\text{Baseline Time}}{\text{Update Time}}$). Rows are sorted in ascending order of the second EBV baseline times. Times for the first EBV are similar across configurations and are thus omitted. Note that floating-point solve times can be inferred from the total time (the first and second EBV times for the baseline configuration are approximately equal).

The update configuration outperformed the baseline for half of the tested problems (the corresponding speedups are marked in bold), attaining upwards of six-fold improvements in the second EBV step. Additionally, all but one of the instances in which the update method was slower had baseline factorization times of less than 0.5 seconds, i.e., these instances were comparatively easier. These results suggest that, for problems where the baseline factorization is already very fast, the fixed computational overhead of the update mechanism (storing the exact factorization, computing the direction vector, etc.) is larger than the time saved by the update.

To further delve into the results, we focus on the solvers' performance on specific instances. There were zero mismatches across the first and second EBV steps for two problems, namely "pilot.ja" and "pilot.we". In a way, this provides the best use case for the update configuration since, unlike

the baseline configuration, it detects that no changes to the current exact factorization are needed. Yet, it is worth pointing out that QSOpt_ex should stop after the initial EBV step in these cases. This discrepancy seems to originate from the additional floating-point subroutines that occur before and after the EBV step. More specifically, we theorize that it is caused by the presence of roundoff errors in the variable bounds that are used to judge feasibility, which are corrected once precision is increased by the warm-start procedure.

The update configuration attained its worst performance on “stat96v5”, the instance with the highest overall computational time—it even timed out during preliminary testing. While its mismatch ratio was moderate (3.6%), the absolute number of mismatches was relatively high (85). This outcome highlights the issue of “fill-in,” where repeated updates cause the sparse L and U factors to become progressively denser, resulting in significant slowdown. This issue is exacerbated by the use of exact arithmetic due to the memory size needed to store non-zeros in the numerator and denominator of each LU factorization coefficient (see Escobedo et al. (2018)). Empirical analysis of the solver logs revealed that while the initial LU updates for this problem took ~ 5 seconds, the final updates in the sequence ballooned to over 90 seconds each. This demonstrates that beyond a certain absolute threshold, full re-factorization is more efficient, which aligns with standard practice of floating-point solvers (Chvátal 1983).

4.2. Performance on Additional Instances Obtained via Perturbation

The above results suggest that the effectiveness of the multi-column LU update is influenced by multiple factors including the mismatch-based threshold at which the subroutine is executed and the baseline factorization times. To further analyze these factors, we perform a second set of computational tests on instances generated by perturbing those in the original compilation.

We begin with the 29 problems that passed the initial filters of requiring extended precision and having up to 500 mismatches, but excluding the subsequent mismatch ratio constraint; “Stat96v5” is excluded due to its high computational cost, reducing the set to 28 problems. We generate new instances from these problems through small perturbations, expecting that such changes could create additional computational difficulty. Specifically, given a constraint set $Ax \leq b$, we add a small perturbation ϵ , with $\epsilon \in \{10^{-1}, 10^{-2}, \dots, 10^{-12}\}$, to: (i) the right-hand side coefficients b , (ii) the constraint matrix coefficients A , or (iii) both A and b . This results in 36 new instances for each original problem, which gives a total of 1,008 new problems. We then tested the dataset and filtered the results using the previous process to only consider those problems eligible for exact LU updates. Table 2 reports multiple speedup statistics (median, mean, std, min, max) as well as their original benchmark results for the 2nd EBV over all instances that require extended precision (count). Rows are sorted by ascending median speedups (over the relevant instances of each problem).

The perturbation method yielded additional numerically challenging instances, especially from problems already exhibiting high computational cost. We attribute this to the numerical conditioning of their basis matrices, where small perturbations caused large changes in the corresponding factorizations. Perturbations did not succeed in generating numerically challenging variants for only two base problems, namely, “50v10_LP” and “uccase9_LP”; they are thus omitted from Table 2. Among the problems that initially failed to meet the 5% mismatch threshold, several perturbed variants triggered LU updates. Although most of these cases did not produce measurable speedups, this behavior suggests that perturbations could serve as a mechanism to generate new benchmark instances from problems that previously did not enter extended precision.

Figure 4 visualizes the speedup statistics shown in Table 2 using a box and whisker plot, for each base problem (the x-axis is ordered by ascending median first baseline EBV time for each base set). This second set of experiments confirms some of the previous findings, for example that

Table 2 Perturbations Generated 421 New Challenging Problems (Excluding Original Problems)

Base Problem	Count	Median Speedup	Mean Speedup	Std	Min Speedup	Max Speedup	Original Speedup
cbs-cta_LP	2	0.017	0.017	0.003	0.015	0.020	0.019
neos-4722843-widden_LP	4	0.097	0.103	0.016	0.091	0.127	0.153
etamacro	4	0.267	0.269	0.024	0.242	0.300	-
large009	35	0.352	0.371	0.159	0.050	0.695	0.381
delf033	36	0.375	0.393	0.190	0.126	0.926	0.327
gen-ip054_LP	4	0.401	0.398	0.065	0.328	0.461	-
large035	11	0.438	0.581	0.254	0.345	0.931	-
large001	32	0.448	0.464	0.262	0.016	1.093	0.473
nesm	27	0.458	0.475	0.108	0.263	0.687	0.459
cycle	28	0.535	0.553	0.077	0.452	0.732	0.536
large036	12	0.760	0.755	0.317	0.404	1.210	-
ger50_17_trans_LP	6	0.844	0.844	0.014	0.827	0.868	0.886
ge	12	1.154	1.094	0.182	0.748	1.401	1.227
dff001	20	1.185	1.245	0.447	0.232	2.049	1.235
ran14x18-disj-8_LP	7	1.247	1.957	1.668	0.663	5.486	1.967
pilot87	28	1.625	2.023	1.207	0.983	6.830	2.008
pilot.ja	22	2.641	2.360	1.484	0.471	4.339	5.294
dano3_3_LP	29	2.871	3.051	1.713	0.842	8.112	3.680
dano3_5_LP	29	2.886	3.053	1.703	0.847	8.069	3.672
pilot	28	2.892	3.207	1.238	1.787	6.220	3.260
pilot.we	19	3.037	2.559	0.833	1.192	3.300	1.204
model6	26	3.534	3.875	1.354	1.764	6.226	2.987
d2q06c	23	5.087	4.816	1.234	1.957	6.393	6.196

Figure 4 Perturbing the Original Problems Generates Many LPs that Benefit from Multi-Column LU Updates

problems with expensive EBV steps tend to yield higher speedups. It also enables the inspection of unresolved questions including the comparative effect of the absolute number of mismatches and the mismatch ratio on computational times. Figure 5 shows that both mismatch count (left) and mismatch ratio (right) exhibit a negative correlation with speedup, but the relationship with the former is notably stronger. Once the number of updates exceeds approximately 60, the efficiency of multi-column updates drops sharply, suggesting that a full re-factorization becomes more efficient

Figure 5 # No. of Mismatches Exhibits a Stronger Negative Correlation with Speedup than Mismatch Ratio

beyond this point. By contrast, the mismatch ratio shows a weaker effect: even up to about 5%, there still are instances where the speedup remains roughly neutral. This supports the conjecture that the absolute number of updates, rather than their relative proportion, is the dominant factor in determining whether the exact multi-column LU updates are beneficial.

5. Conclusion

This work demonstrates that multi-column LU updates can accelerate basis validation subroutines of exact linear programming solvers, particularly for instances where the cost of full exact factorization is prohibitively high. While the results indicate that factorization fill-in and storage overhead pose limitations, there are additional directions for improving performance. A first direction is to replace the rigid floating-point precision increases currently used by QSOpt_ex with an approach that adjusts these boosts dynamically based on problem-specific properties (e.g., sparsity, approximate conditioning, etc.). A second direction is to adapt and implement exact LU update methods based on integer-preserving arithmetic (Escobedo and Moreno-Centeno 2017). Integer arithmetic-based algorithms have been shown to outperform their rational arithmetic counterparts, in both space and time complexity, when constructing LU factorizations and using them in forward and backward substitution (Escobedo et al. 2018, Lourenco et al. 2019). Finally, the multi-column updates could be expanded to improve the performance of exact mixed integer programming solvers, where exact LP methods are a bottleneck (Cook et al. 2011, Hoen and Gleixner 2025). In this context, the branch-and-bound framework, which requires solving vast trees of closely related LP relaxations, naturally presents the low-mismatch conditions where the update algorithm could be beneficial.

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